

VEGETATION AS AN BIOLOGICAL MEASURE FOR FLOOD CONTROL

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SUMMARY: The aim of research is improvement of the quality of the landscape structure of Jaša Tomić village for adequate flood protection. A multidisciplinary approach to the researched problem was contributed to the economic, social and environmental perspective. Based on analysis of existing conditions, and guided by the experiences of international examples, it has been proposed a biological method of flood control for the banks of Jaša Tomić village. This method of defense is implemented by connecting hydrophilic fragments of native forests, but also by improving vegetative fund of non-indigenous species adaptable to the environmental conditions.

Key words: *flood, the biological form of defense, floodplain vegetation.*

INTRODUCTION

Due to extremely high water levels in a rivers, water from their beds raises over the coast and flows surrounding area. Floods are natural large-scale phenomena that can endanger human life or cause damage to a large extent. They can be viewed as a natural hazards and as a natural risks. Natural hazard means any natural phenomenon that could be a danger to human life, property or human interests. If flooding occurs in a limited duration, in a clearly defined geographic area, with accurate consequences and if the interactions between humans and natural processes resulting in significant property damage, injury or loss of life, then a natural hazard becomes a natural risk.

The essence of understanding the natural phenomena like floods is dealing with their history. These are the events that come over and again, and thus the study of their past will provide appropriate information for reducing a degree of an impact that they can bring to people and environment in the present or future. Floods can be regulated in several ways. First of all, by legal policies, monitoring of meteorological forecast, by

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raising the flood protection facilities, and by biological methods. Raising the protective forest belts along the streams brings positive effects, because does not allow the local snow accumulation and soil erosion; it can improve air mode, and it could implement a surface water runoff into the interior of the land (Lješević, 2002). At the same time, these protective forest belts could reduce the hazardous effects of flooding consequences to the environment.

Serbia has been struggling with flood hazard far away in the past. The largest floods were recorded in the basin of Tisa, Danube and Sava (Gavrilović, 1981) - the three largest rivers in Vojvodina (Table 1.). The first observations of water levels on rivers in Serbia started in the first half of the nineteenth century and the first one was in the territory of Vojvodina. The oldest hydrological station was founded in the 1819 in the city of Novi Sad, then in the city of Novi Bečej (began its work after 36 years). As Gavrilović (1981) said, in the period of thirty years, since 1955 to 1985, in Serbia the floods with catastrophic proportions has been occurred every two years. One of the major flood occurred in 1955 when the total damage amounted to about 9.3 million old dinars, of which only in Vojvodina the damage was estimated at 7.3 billion old dinars. Ten years later in 1965 the major watercourses affected another floods of large-scale.

Table 1. Built constructions of the embankment of important river basins in Vojvodina

Tabela 1. Izgrađenost nasipa važnih rečnih slivova u Vojvodini

river/ <i>reka</i>	length of the constructed embankments/ <i>dužina izgrađenog nasipa (km)</i>
Dunav	304,16
Tisa	289,63
Sava	119,77
Tamiš	86,04
Stari i Plovni Begej	127,80
other embankments	532,62

Tamiš with Begej belongs to the categories of the rivers, which were the first one that started with reclamation works in the Pannonian Plain since 1728 in the Austro-Hungarian period. Large floods in the past were associated with Tamiš river, and in the year of 2005 this river has experienced perhaps the largest ever recorded water spills on its banks. The catastrophic flood completely flooded the village Jaša Tomić, located in the far east of central Banat, in the municipality Sečanj (Grupa autora, 1998).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

As Kandilioti and Makropoulos (2011) pointed out, an appropriate method for effective study of the area potentially affected by floods, should provide a detailed analysis of a researched space, according to the size of the problem, and such methods, that require extensive data and considerably effort, can not be rely on modeling. Also, the same authors suggest that the most appropriate approach to this issue is an analysis of multiple criteria, which this paper seeks.

In order to adequately regulate the floods in the village of Jaša Tomić, also to built a defensive model against the flooding and applicable to the entire territory of Vojvodina, it has been joined multidisciplinary to the study of the regulation of this problem through a social, an economic and ecological aspects. On the one hand, through the

comparative method, there have been compared examples of the world practice (biological methods of flood protection), with local experience and it has been given a guideline for further activities in the study area. On the other hand, in order to improve future planning and space it was analyzed the current state of landscape structure within the village Jaša Tomić by making an unique check lists. Making a check lists serve as the method of assessment and the method of evaluation of existing space conditions, whether it is for an inventory of existing conditions, the development of the planning ideas or simply for the state of environmental impact assessment. Check list conducted in this study was done on the basis of the relevant examples, which were given by Kandilioti and Makropoulos (2011). Investigated parameters and criteria were adapted to the issue of the work involved. In particular, the selection criteria for evaluating the natural complex planning, were based on general theoretical knowledge, intuition, experience, attributes fields for which the plan is working, based on current needs and planning practice in Serbia.

The survey was conducted during 2010 and 2011 year. In order to encourage biological methods of flood protection, the work gravitated to examination of the present state of the vegetation, so the check list that was used for the analysis was the check list of the space greenery (Table 2.) throughout the evaluation of the composition, form, color, mosaic elements and so on.

Analysis of the greenery, carried out in the relation to the examined criteria, which were based on the desire for the formation of high landscape architectural quality, environmental and spatial composition. By observing the vegetation analysis, the criteria were evaluated in order to obtain biodiversity and bio-engineering diverse composition. There have been set out following positive parameters: a balanced relationship between broadleaves and conifers, expressed vegetation floors and composition in accordance with the natural characteristics of the space, good maintenance of open space, its wealth of colors and smooth shadows and light ratio, as well as physical and visual barriers. As a negative remaining parameters there have been assessed values within the stated test of the checklist.

Table 2. Check list for analyzing the space greenery
Tabela 2. Lista procene postojećeg stanja zelenila

Category of the greenery/ <i>Kategorija zelenila</i>	Number/ <i>Broj</i>		(%)		General mark/ <i>Opšta ocena</i>
conifers	-		-		positive negative
broadleaves	-		100%		
note	It is hard to speak about exactly number of trees because they are in the form of masses.				
Greenery floor/ <i>Spratnost zelenila</i>	<10%	10-40%	40-70%	100%	General mark/ <i>Opšta ocena</i>

high greenery	-	-	x	-	positive negative					
middle greenery	x	-	-	-						
low greenery	-	-	-	-						
ground flowering greenery	-	-	-	-						
lawn	-	x	-	-						
note	Middle greenery is a wild, and direct reflects to the greenery floor.									
Composition of the greenery/ <i>Kompozicija zelenila</i>	<10%	10-40%	40-70%	100%	General mark/ <i>Opšta ocena</i>					
groups	-	-	-	x	positive negative					
tree lines	-	-	-	-						
soliter trees - soliters	-	-	-	-						
note	The composition is monotonous.									
Mark/ <i>Ocena</i>	Bad/ <i>Loše</i>	Good/ <i>Dobro</i>	Excellent/ <i>Odlično</i>		General mark/ <i>Opšta ocena</i>					
maintaining	-	x	-		positive negative					
note	The environment is not too degraded, and the maintenance is solid.									
Space feeling/ <i>Osećaj u prostoru</i>	Monochrome/ <i>Monohrom</i>		Reach in colours/ <i>Bogat bojama</i>		General mark/ <i>Opšta ocena</i>					
coloring/ <i>kolorit</i>	x		-		positive negative					
	Sunned areas/ <i>Osunčanost</i>		Shaded areas/ <i>Senka</i>							
light	20%	40%	60%	80%		20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
	Geometric/ <i>Geometrijska</i>		Organic/ <i>Organska</i>							
form	-		x							
note	A dominance of green colour is emphasized.									
Position/ <i>Pozicija</i>	Positive contribution/ <i>Pozitivan doprinos-opis</i>			Negative contribution/ <i>Negativan doprinos-opis</i>						
физичке и визуелне баријере	The protective role of greenery is highlighted.			Physical separation of the settlements and the river.						
GENERAL MARK OF THE PRESENT STATE OF SPACE GREENERY/ OPŠTA OCENA STANJA ZELENILA U PROSTORU										
Vegetation is balanced. There is a uniform relation between the mass and open space. The space is very monotonous, mainly represented by poplars and invasive species in the first floor of vegetation. There is a lot of open grass areas, which is evaluated relatively positively, because it opens up pleasant visions to the Romanian coast.										

RESULTS

By analyzing the the present state of the space and by conducting the check list, it was observed an absolute representation of broadleaves. The presence of conifers and other relevant plant species was not observed. In this way it was created one monotonous and monochrome space, and the estimation of this parameter is negative. The composition of vegetation in the area is very modest - one hundred percentage of the groups'

vegetative form presence, so it could be said that there are the positive values of this area in the terms of composition. The form is organic character, where forests and meadows alternating, at the same time light and shadow (Figure 2). The form was evaluated positively. The floors of greenery (Figure 1) are not clearly expressed. There is a domination of high greenery and the score is negative. In the area of landscape structure it has been noticed the fragmentation of hydrophilic forests (Figure 4.A), which reflect negatively on the existing biodiversity. The existing vegetation is very good potential for the creation of coastal water protection greenery. On the other hand vegetation alone gives the impression of physical space barriers, by surrounding the settlement, which was assessed as negative effect.

Figure 1. Percentages of green floors
Slika.1. Procentualno izražena spratnost zelenila

Figure 2. Space in the terms of percentages of sunshine
Slika 2. Procentualno izražena osunčanost područja

In the rational use and protection of river water areas and streams, one of the main measure is the regulation of their water-protective vegetation (Vujković, 2003). Vegetation affects the reduction of groundwater levels in the lower flows, thanks to absorptive power of the underground parts of the plants. It affects that the water slowly drains to streams, thus reducing the likelihood of spring flooding, and creates more abundant waterways (Vujković, 2003). According to Vujković (2003) it is also pointed out that the forest and parks plantations on the banks of river waters, fully express their capabilities to chain the ground and river embankment, so their waterproof function is very valuable. Precisely, in these areas that are clearly expressed soil erosion.

Since the coast is exposed to the strong intensive water-blows and to changing the water level, field afforestation is desirable, in order to provide stability and faster absorption in the period of the increasing the flood waters. On the other hand, it is necessary to pursue the connection of forest fragments (Figure 4.B) with the aim of restoring

and improving the biodiversity habitats (Turner, 2003). In this process, presence of the monocultures should be avoided and the work should be direct to diversity of the vegetative composition, in biological terms, but in the floors also.

The studied area belongs to alluvial - hydrophilic forest, type of wetland forests of alliance *Alnion glutinosae* (Table 3), forests of white willow and poplar alliance *Salicion albae* (Table 4) and oak forests association *Genisto elatae - Quercetum roboris* (Table 5), so their planting is recommending. However, in order to create a harmonious composition if it proves as feasible, it should strive to introduction of the non-indigenous species, resistant to the natural space conditions. In the case of Jaša Tomić those are species resistant to wet areas, salt and clay soils (Table 6) (Jović et al., 1996).

Table 3. Swamp forests of alliance *Alnion glutinosae*

Tabela 3. Močvarne šume crne jove sveze *Alnion glutinosa*

woody forms/ <i>drvenaste forme</i>	herbaceous forms/ <i>zeljaste forme</i>
<i>Salix cinerea</i> L., <i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i> Vahl., <i>Alnus glutinosa</i> L.	<i>Phragmites communis</i> Trin., <i>Glyceria maxima</i> (Hartm.) Holmb., <i>Eleocharis palustris</i> L., <i>Carex elongate</i> L., <i>Carex leporine</i> L., <i>Juncus effuses</i> L., <i>Galium palustre</i> L.

Table 6. Potential forest and shrub speaces tolerante on salts in the ground

Tabela 6. Izbor potencijalnih vrsta drveća i žbunja tolerantnih na soli

species tolerant to the presence of salts in the soil/ <i>vrste tolerantne na prisustvo soli u zemljištu</i>	tree and shrub species/ <i>vrste drveća i žbunja</i>
very tolerant	<i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i> Vahl., <i>Chamaecyparis lawsoniana</i> (A. Murray) Parl., <i>Thuja orientalis</i> L., <i>Tamarix tetrandra</i> L.
middle tolerant	<i>Acer platanoides</i> L., <i>Acer campestre</i> L., <i>Sophora japonica</i> L., <i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L., <i>Pyrus piraster</i> L.
poorly tolerant	<i>Morus alba</i> L., <i>Gleditsia triachantos</i> L., <i>Ribes aureum</i> Pursh., <i>Caragana arborescens</i> Lam., <i>Rhus typhifina</i> L.
tolerant to the salt in soil	<i>Platanus acerifolia</i> (Aiton) Willd., <i>Malus silvestris</i> L., <i>Maclura aurantiaca</i> Nutt., <i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq.

The research has shown that the space itself is very rich in monocultures and these are mostly species of willows and poplars in 90% of the examined territory. The fragments are observed with *Alnus glutinosa* L. and some other species adaptive to occasional flooded areas.

At water flows, largely made up from broadleaved forests, the most favorable planting is with *Alnus glutinosa* L. However, in order to avoid the already mentioned danger of monocultures, but also to achieve biodiversity and ecological effects (changes of the light and darkness, heat flow of various air streams etc.) besides planting *Alnus glutinosa* L. it is recommending the planting of other plant species as so woody as herbaceous. So called "living material" involves the usage of *Alnus glutinosa* L., *Quercus robur* L., *Salix alba* L. etc., depending on space conditions (Cvejić, 1999).

Alnus glutinosa L. root penetrating up to 1.5 m deep in the ground water in the form of a dense palisade, ensuring lower parts of slopes from erosion. Fine roots in the zone of water level changes, providing the upper surface of erosion, affect at the formation of biotopes and eventually make the image of landscape beautifully. Young plants are planted at a distance 100cm - 150cm, holes are up to 20cm - 40cm above the middle summer waters. If the planting is done in a row, then striking the coast should be planted with *Alnus glutinosa* L. and the interior could be planted with some other species. But if it is planted in two rows, then the internal row should exclusively be from *Alnus glutinosa* L., and the external from the other species (Figure 3) (Cvejić, 1999).

Figure 3. Protecting the river's coast with the roots of state of the research area *Alnus glutinosa* L. (1.- *Alnus glutinosa* L., 2.- other species)

Slika 3. Osiguranje obala korenom *Alnus glutinosa* L. istraživanog područja (1.- *Alnus glutinosa* L., 2.- druge vrste)

A.

B.

Figure 4. A. Map of the present state of the research area

B. Map of the planning state of the research area

Slika 4. A. Karta postojećeg stanja istraživanog područja

B. Karta planiranog stanja istraživanog područja

Also, for the purpose of flood control and avoiding the formation of single crops, and according to natural conditions it is proposed a plantation of a certain types of clones such as clones *Populus x euramericana* Dode (Guinier) and *Populus deltoides* W.Bartram ex Humphry Marshall (Orlović et al., 2006).

In order to create a dynamic, functional (in the purpose of flood control), and above all colorful composition, which in its current condition rated negatively, it must not be neglected the aquatic flora as well. In the case of Jaša Tomić it is suggested an emergent vegetation of alliance *Phragmites communis*, which proved to be resistant in this area. On the other hand, one should carefully choose the species of this alliance, in order not to cover whole rivers' bed due to an expansive spreading (Džigurski et al., 2011). The consequence of it is directly related to the flooding of river banks.

CONCLUSION

The floods in Serbia have increase ratio, as well as water levels. Almost every year some waterways leave their beds and flooding larger or smaller areas, thus endangering people and their material wealth. Funds invested now in the protection and flood defense can not be even remotely comparable to the effects that the foods cause, whether there are a visible consequences or with a prolonged negative effects on the environ-

ment. Technology and organization of flood protection must be constantly improved, and this work shows a little neglected way of flood control - biological methods.

Formation of landscape composition must be first in accordance with certain natural characteristics considered to be appropriate and acceptable for the environment and its users. Priority should be directed towards the restoration of native vegetation. However in the process of designing landscape composition it may be used non-indigenous species as well, resistant to the natural characteristics of the relevant settlement. These are figures that should form the basis for further planning and project structure of the landscape composition.

REFERENCE

- CVEJIĆ, J.: Uređivanje predela - inženjersko-biološke mere. Univerzitet u Beogradu, Šumarski fakultet Beograd, pp. 56-134, 1999.
- DŽIGURSKI, D., KNEŽEVIĆ, A., NIKOLIĆ, LJ., LJEVNAIĆ-MAŠIĆ B.: Emergent vegetation in main canals of the HS DTD in the region of Bačka. Contemporary agriculture, 60(1-2)73-79, 2011.
- GAVRILOVIĆ, LJ.: Poplave u SR Srbiji u XX veku. Srpsko geografsko društvo, Beograd, pp. 1- 118, 1981.
- GRUPA AUTORA: Zaštita od poplava u Srbiji. Institut za vodoprivredu "Jaroslav Černi"- Beograd, Zavod za uređenje vodnih tokova, pp. 1- 33, 1998.
- IVANIŠEVIĆ, P., NINIĆ-TODOROVIĆ, J., SAPUNDŽIĆ, M., VLATKOVIĆ, S.: Mogućnost podizanja zelenila na zemljištu tipa solonec u funkciji zaštite životne sredine Doma za decu i omladinu u Veterniku. Eko-konferencija'95, Zaštita životne sredine gradova i prigradskih naselja – sa međunarodnim učešćem, zbornik radova, Ekološki pokret grada Novog Sada, Novi Sad, pp. 211-218, 1995.
- JOVIĆ, N., TOMIĆ, Z., JOVIĆ, D.: Tipologija šuma. Univerzitet u Beogradu, Šumarski fakultet, pp. 101 – 145, 1996.
- KANDILIOTI, G., MAKROPOULOS, C.: Preliminary flood risk assessment: the case of Athens. Springer Science+Business Media B.V., Nat Hazards, DOI 10.1007/s11069-011-9930-5, pp.1 – 15, 2011.
- LJEŠEVIĆ, M.: *Ruralna ekologija*. Univerzitet u Beogradu, Geografski fakultet, pp. 214 – 255, 2002.
- ORLOVIĆ, S., PILIPOVIĆ, A., GALIĆ, Z., KLAŠNJA, B., RADOSAVLJEVIĆ, N.: Varijabilnost i adaptabilnost klonova topola, Savremena poljoprivreda, 55(5)13–21, 2006.
- SALVAI, A., NIKOLIĆ, A., GALONJA, M., ĐAKONOVIĆ, S., ZARIĆ, B., MATIN, Z.: Odbrana od poplava – stručno informativna brošura. JVP „Vode Vojvodine“, Novi Sad, pp. 1-18, 2010.
- TURNER, T.: Landscape planning and environmental impact design. Routledge, Taylor&Francis Group, London and New York, pp. 280 -317, 2003.
- VUJKOVIĆ LJ.: Pejzažna arhitektura – planiranje i projektovanje. Univerzitet u Beogradu, Šumarski fakultet, Beograd, Univerzitet u Beogradu, pp. 28 – 33, 194 – 195, 2003.

VEGETACIJA KAO BIOLOŠKA MERA ODBRANE OD POPLAVA

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Izvod

Cilj rada je unapređenje kvaliteta predeone strukture naselja Jaša Tomić radi adekvatne odbrane od poplava. Multidisciplinarni pristup istraživanom problemu doprineo je sagledavanju problema iz ekonomskog, sociološkog i ekološkog ugla. Na osnovu analize postojećeg stanja, a vođeni iskustvima svetskih primera, na obalama naselja Jaša Tomić predlaže se biološki način odbrane od poplava. Ovaj način odbrane se sprovodi povezivanjem fragmenata autohtonih higrofilnih šuma, ali i unapređenjem vegetacijskog fonda alohtonim biljnim vrstama prilagodljivim uslovima sredine.

Ključne reči: poplave, biološki vid odbrane, vegetacija plavnih područja.

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